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Innovation and Practice in Constructing World Class Engineering

Education: A Case Study of Tsinghua University

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China is promoting the Double World-Class Construction Project, which aims to constructing world-class universities and world-class disciplines. As the largest discipline area in China's higher education, engineering education is key to the development of higher education and plays a vital role in the process of Double World-Class Construction. Tsinghua University is one of the top universities in China and having great advantages in engineering disciplines. It has been ranked the best university for Engineering by U.S. News & World Report. The strategy innovation and practice for engineering education plays a leading and exemplary role for the universities and colleges in China. The paper will analyze the strategical background for engineering education in China and introduce Tsinghua's strategic thinking and innovative practice in constructing world-class engineering disciplines.

Key word: Double World-Class Construction, Tsinghua University, Engineering Education

In recent years, the Double World-Class Construction Project has become a hot topic in China's higher education community. The project aims to construct a number of world class universities and disciplines with Chinese characteristics. This has become the common consensus and action orientation of the key universities, including Tsinghua University. The research and strategic planning on the core issues of teaching, research, international cooperation and resource allocation, are the internal need to enhance the core competitiveness and achieve sustainable development of universities and disciplines, and also the inevitable choice to achieve the goals of "double world-class" construction and promote the comprehensive strength and international competitiveness of higher education in China.

Engineering is the largest discipline area in China's higher education. According to the statistics of the Ministry of Education, the number of engineering undergraduate and graduate students in 2015 accounted for 33% and 36% of the total number of higher education students respectively. ^[1] Engineering education plays a key role in enhancing the strength of higher education. In most influential global rankings, the highest ranking subjects in China's universities are engineering ones. For example, in 2015 and 2016, the engineering discipline of Tsinghua University was ranked first in the world. ^[2] It

can be said that engineering education in some universities has already become the world's leading disciplines. It is the leader of "double world class" construction.

As the leader of the key universities in China, Tsinghua University made the strategic goal of becoming a world class university in the 1980s. Under the sustained support of China's key national strategical projects such as "211 Project" and "985 Project", Tsinghua has gradually established and continuously promoted its global reputation and influence. As the dominant disciplines of Tsinghua, engineering education has won a high academic reputation and will continue to support the development of the university. The paper will analyze the strategical background for engineering education in China and introduce Tsinghua's strategic thinking and innovative practice in constructing world-class engineering disciplines.

I、 The Strategic Significance of Building the World-class Engineering Education

1. Building World-class Engineering Education is an Inevitable Requirement to Enhance China's Global Competitiveness.

According to the World Competitiveness Reports released by the World Economic Forum from 2010 to 2016, China's global competitiveness ranked 26th – 29th^[3] or top 20% among the 144 economies in the world. These ranking results indicated China had certain comparative advantage and had great development potential and prospects. However, according to the evaluation indicator system of world competitiveness, China has few indicators with absolute competitive advantage. These indicators were mainly the scale or volume ones, like the scale of domestic market. China has more indicators with relative or zero competitive advantage, especially "China's technical preparation, innovation and higher education and training were drags on China's competitiveness".^[4] To further enhance China's overall competitiveness, it is necessary to make these indicators become the ones with absolute competitive advantage.

According to the definition of the global competitiveness, "technical preparation" mainly measures the application of new technologies by an economy and the convenience it brought to the economy, including the application and transfer of new technologies, the number of Internet users, and the legal protection of technologies. "Higher education and training" measures the training and supply of talents by colleges and universities, including the scale of colleges and universities, education quality, the training and supply of professional talents, and so on. "Innovation" mainly measures the innovation and R&D ability of an economy, including the quality of scientific research institutions, cooperation between universities and enterprises, the number of scientists and engineers and so on. It can be seen that the development level of engineering education is closely related to the training of engineers and scientists, technical research and development, cooperation between universities and enterprises, and the transfer of scientific and technological achievements. The construction of

world-class engineering education helps to cultivate engineers and technicians with international vision and innovation ability, and improve the global competitiveness.

2. Building World-class Engineering Education is the Basic Prerequisite for a Strong Manufacturing Nation.

The blueprint of Made in China 2025 pointed out that "manufacturing is an important symbol of a country's comprehensive economic strength, the pillar industry of the national economy system, and the leading force of modernization and industrialization." Only with strong manufacturing can we have strong country and nation. However, in the new round of industry revolution, China's manufacturing is "big but not strong", mainly in the aspects of backward technology, serious overcapacity, low profit and low added value. Through the strategic deployment of Made in China 2025, China takes the initiative to cope with the challenges and strengthen the manufacturing industry so as to achieve the upgrading of manufacturing industry.

Engineering Education in China has been providing strong human resources and intellectual support for the national development and construction. Made in China 2025 proposed the basic principle of "talent based". Manufacturing power is bound to powerful talents. Engineering and technological talents are the fundamental prerequisite for building a strong manufacturing nation. China should vigorously carry forward the craftsman spirit to strengthen the training and lifelong education of engineering talents, build a rational and quality manufacturing talent team and improve the social status of engineering talents, so as to promote the realization of the strategic goal of the manufacturing power.

3. Building World-class Engineering Education will Support the One Belt and One Road with Science and Technology Talents

The One Belt and One Road Initiative, which was proposed in 2013, has received wide attention and response of the world. As the initiative continued to develop, engineering and technical talents with a global vision became a bottleneck for Chinese enterprises going abroad. The countries along the Road, especially the developing countries in Asia and Africa, were eager to have depth cooperation with Chinese universities and enterprises to promote the abilities of science and technology talents. The demand, for talents is more urgent. Higher engineering education would play a key role cultivate science and technology talents for both Chinese enterprises and developing countries.

4. Building World-class Engineering Education would help to create a new ecology of Internet + Education.

Internet+ is the usage of Internet as a platform, including the use of mobile Internet, cloud computing, big data, artificial intelligence and information communication technology, to realize the deep integration of various industries and form a new economic and social development pattern based on Internet, so as to comprehensively promote the innovation ability and productivity of the country.

Internet + engineering education will shape a new and equal engineering education mode to change the cognitive style and learning habits of engineering students and thoroughly reform the lifelong learning of engineers. Compared with the traditional education of engineers, the knowledge service which combines the Internet and information technology can break the limitation of time and space and reduce the cost. On the basis of Internet and cloud platform technology, Internet + engineering education can integrate high quality engineering education resources and provide convenient and efficient information tools to effectively meet the need of engineering education.

II、 Practice of Building World-class Engineering Education in Tsinghua University

1. Cultivating the World - class Engineering Talents

The most fundamental task of world-class engineering education is to cultivate top innovative engineering talents. On the road of building a world class university, Tsinghua University is committed to cultivating the leading and innovative talents for all sectors of the society. Over the years, Tsinghua has always integrated teaching, learning and doing in practice education and focused on the students' ability of innovation and practice. In particular, Tsinghua launched "Xuetang program" in 2009. The program selected outstanding undergraduate students from the fields of mathematics, physics, computer science and mechanics, and built a high-end, open and international learning and communication platform for them. The program comprehensively integrated the advantages of all disciplines of Tsinghua and effectively led the overall quality of the engineering education. The computer science program has been praised by international peers as the best undergraduate education. And the graduates of the electronic engineering were globally accepted as best candidates for graduate programs in top universities around the world.

2. Propose Leading Concept of Engineering Education

In the past 107 years, the engineering educationists of Tsinghua have developed a unique concept of engineering education based on China's national conditions and advanced international educational concepts.

After 1952, Tsinghua gradually evolved into a comprehensive university with advantages in engineering disciplines. Jiang Nanxiang, president of the time, summarized the mission of Tsinghua as "the cradle of engineers". He advocated "real gun" for graduation design, which required students participate in real world engineering projects. In the early period of new China, this philosophy fit the urgent needs of the nation and Tsinghua cultivated a large number of engineering talents for the country.

In twenty-first Century, with the change of industrial structure and the progress of engineering technology, social development has put forward new requirements for engineering and technical talents. Every country in the world were aware of the change, and began to redesign the engineering education programs. The American National Academy of Engineering published *Engineer 2020* and envision the future and predict the roles that engineers will play in the future.

Tsinghua has also acutely grasped this historical trend. Engineering education was strengthened with the general education on the basis of inheriting historical ideas. At the end of last century, Tsinghua proposed the idea of fostering talents with "deep foundation, wide caliber, compound type and high level". In 2014, Tsinghua began to implement "Three-in-One" education model, which included values molding, ability training and knowledge imparting. The goals of engineering education were expanded to training students to have sound personality, broad foundation, innovative thinking, global vision and social responsibility. In 2017, Tsinghua University began to integrate undergraduate enrollment into 16 major categories. Engineering education involved 8 major categories. On the one hand, the reform gave full play to the disciplinary advantage of Tsinghua as a comprehensive to train all-round talents through general education. On the other hand, the integration of disciplines has broken the pattern of specialized division and expanded the employment orientation of graduates. For example, mechanical category included mechanical engineering, measurement and control technology and instruments, vehicle engineering, energy and power engineering and so on. The core courses would be refined and optimized according to the knowledge structure, ability and quality needs of high quality professionals.

3. Establishing World-level Quality Assurance System for Engineering Education

The quality of education is key to the construction of great power engineering education. Tsinghua based on its own development goals, put forward high quality standards and actively accept more stringent assessment and evaluation to ensure that the level of engineering education can be recognized internationally and the engineering education could reach the level of the world-class universities.

Since 2009, Tsinghua has initiated the international assessment of disciplines, to examined and promoted the construction of disciplines through the efforts of international peers. Up to now, 16 international assessments have been completed, 11

of which were engineering disciplines. The international evaluation made benchmark with the development status and trend of the world-class universities. Through the diagnostic evaluation, the development level of the disciplines was tested, the weakness of the disciplines was found. Experts from the world-class universities evaluated the teaching, scientific research, faculty team of the disciplines, and provided pertinent opinions and suggestions. The university and department adjusted policies and support to the disciplines. Through the preparation of self-evaluation reports, disciplines carried out a comprehensive and in-depth review of the status, and constantly found problems and sought solutions. Some disciplines have already carried out two and three rounds of international assessment. And there have been obvious changes and progress.

4. Building World - class Platform for Global Cooperation

Global cooperation is an important feature of world-class engineering education. It is an active choice for universities and engineering departments to integrate high quality education resources and improve international competitiveness. It is of great significance to promote the understanding of different engineering culture, strengthening academic exchange of engineering education, and cultivating engineering talents who can participate in international competition. Tsinghua University was born with distinct feature of globalization. It was a pre-school for students who would go study in America. Many famous faculty of early stage Tsinghua, such as Qian Sanqiang, Zhang Guangdou, Ye Qisun, Zhang Wei, were the outstanding ones from the pre-school.

With the deepening of national reform and opening up and the continuous change of international situation, the global cooperation of Tsinghua has gradually moved from passive to initiative, from going out to mutually communication, from actively participation to initiatively leading. The cooperated countries not only involved the developed countries, but also expanded to developing countries, in order to promote equality, peace and tolerance around the world. The international cooperation projects not only involved students exchange and faculty visit, but also expanded to scientific research and social services. Tsinghua is dealing with the major engineering and technology problems and environmental development in the world with all the world-class universities, enterprises, research institutions and international organizations.

In June 2016, the International Center for Engineering Education (ICEE), officially approved by the 38th General Assembly of UNESCO Member States, launched at Tsinghua. The center was the first UNESCO center focusing on engineering education. It is jointly sponsored by the Chinese Academy of Engineering and Tsinghua University. It will support the UNESCO action plans to carry out multilateral cooperation. For the ICEE will provide engineering personnel training for countries along the One Belt and One Road, especially African countries, to eradicate poverty, promote gender equality and coordinate regional development.

5. Carry on World-class Engineering Education Research

From a worldwide perspective, engineering universities and colleges bear many responsibilities and obligations in the process of development. According to the requirements and characteristics of engineering disciplines, faculties should explore the problems in the process of cultivating engineering talents. Teaching and academic research are always the professional requirements of faculty, and also the spiritual tradition of higher education. Under the background of knowledge economy, scientific research and academic activities related to engineering education are directly linked to the quality and competitive of engineering disciplines. High quality engineering education research is an effective way to improve the competitive of engineering disciplines. Tsinghua has always taken engineering education research as one essential responsibility. It serves the teaching and practice of the engineering education, serves the national engineering education policy decisions, and pays attention to the global engineering education issues. On the process of building a world-class university, the engineering education researches in Tsinghua put more emphasis on serving the strategic needs of the country and promoting global development and social progress.

The engineering education researches in Tsinghua has always been committed to serving the reform of the university, and the reform of the national engineering education. The research areas involved the quality assessment of higher engineering education, report on engineer abilities, and the construction of global engineering capability system, etc. The researches has both thoughts and suggestions on the macro problems related to engineering education system and structure, organization and management, and also the micro questions on curriculum and student development.

Big data era has brought opportunities and challenges for engineering, science and technology. Big data has become a new and important strategic resource. Engineering education research needs more and more support of big data. Big data analysis is changing the thinking mode and research methods of engineering education research. ICEE, with the support of CAE, created a sub center of engineering education knowledge, which is one of the sub centers of UNESCO's international Knowledge Center for Engineering, Science and Technology (IKCEST). The building of IKCEST system platform, will support the UNESCO action plans, and effectively integrate the global engineering education information resources to facilitate the exchange and cooperation of international engineering education.

6. Outputting World - class Online Resources

In the era of digitalized knowledge economy, knowledge is increasingly showing the form of networking and digitalization. Online education has been widely recognized by the society. It has greatly changed the learning methods of engineering students and the on-the-job training methods of practice engineers. It has a profound influence on the traditional concept of higher education, the educational system and the teaching mode.

Engineering disciplines have to take the initiative to adapt to new methods and new technology of information society. High quality online education resources, commercial operation mode, good interactive platform, free global learning, will be an important basis for assessing world-class engineering education. Tsinghua has always been the leader of distance education and online education in China. In 2013, Tsinghua officially joined the online education platform edX and become one of the first Asian universities in edX.

Massive Open Online Course (MOOC) provides an open, flexible and shared mode of communication and learning. MOOC not only provides curriculum resources to the learners, but also the application of learning analysis technology. It is a mix of face-to-face teaching, online learning and mixed learning model, and can reshape the role of teachers to meet the needs of learners' autonomy learning and lifelong learning. In 2014, Tsinghua launched the world's first Chinese MOOC platform, Xuetang Online. At present, Xuetang Online has run number of high quality courses from Tsinghua University, Peking University, Stanford University, Massachusetts Institute of Technology, University of California at Berkeley and so on. The courses covered many fields such as engineering, computer, art and so on. About 7,000,000 users from 180 countries are using the platform for online learning. The daily average access of the online platform is 640,000 and the peak value is 400,000. While actively launching high quality MOOC courses, Tsinghua has initiated and actively organized the MOOC industry standard. The world-class online education can only be realized under the support of the government, the leadership of universities and the participation of enterprises, which will create an open and win-win situation.

In short, building a world-class engineering education is the current and long-term strategy of our country. Adhering to the concept of inheritance, excellence and innovation, engineering education should cultivate world-class engineering talents, carry out first-rate engineering education research, contributing high level engineering education resources, and making world-wide contribution to realize the China's responsibility in the world.

¹ Ministry of Education, Educational Statistics 2015. http://www.moe.edu.cn/s78/A03/moe_560/jytjsj_2015/.

² http://www.360doc.com/content/16/1028/23/6558757_602216795.shtml

³ WEF. World Competitiveness Reports [R]. 2010-2016, <https://www.weforum.org/reports>

⁴ Wang Sun Yu, Xie Zhe Ping, Zhang Yu. Talent and Competition: the Strategy Formulation of Future Engineers Cultivation in China. [J]. Tsinghua Journal of Education. 2016(5):1-10.